

DETERMINANTS OF CUSTOMER SWITCHING INTENTION IN PAKISTAN: A CASE OF CELLULAR SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

The basic aim of this research is to find out the correlation (hypothesis) between the informational justice, interpersonal justice, procedural justice, distributive justice to switching intention. The data was collected on the independent variables and dependent variable which were distributive justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, procedural justice and switching intentions of the customers. The data was collected through questionnaires from the customers of the mobile phone services in Pakistan. The sample size is 450. This research is only talk about one industry which is mobile phone services industry. So, all of the results which are getting from this research cannot be applied in other industries. The data will not be helpful for other than the mobile phone services. These are the limitations for the reader. This research is very helpful or playing a significant part for the experts of the Pakistan's marketing industry of mobile phone services to get the maximum information about their consumers. Pakistan, mobile phone services, switching intentions, customer satisfaction, customer behavior, procedural justice, informational justice, interpersonal justice, distributive justice.

Keywords: procedural justice, distributive justice, switching intention, marketing industry, informational justice
JEL Codes: D63, M30

1. INTRODUCTION

In this era of competition, the changing of cellular services from one network to another is a basic issue of users for Tele communication organizations from past decades; since switching behavior demonstrates that the first network is no longer meets the user desires and that the other network is more appealing. Past studies show that the increasing trend of service switching can be incited by value advancements, in-store displays, upgrades or developments in competitive brands, number of accessible brands, chance, changes in quality, or level of satisfaction with the most recent buy. Brand exchanging is most regular with things that have no unusual seen variety in quality inclining over brands. The switching metrics and patterns increase slowly over the last five to six years. There's doubtlessly the pattern has been basically accelerate by the move to computerized. It has decreased the interferences to exchanging and made clients more portable in more ways than one.

The standard of value and execution of the administration can be instrumental in changing; endorsers should be capable to call client lines and get sufficient offer assistance. They do need to be put on an endless hold. Client's help offer assistance lines need to give supporters quick help, they should be ensured that ought to issue emerge with their accounts, they will discover help. An administration gave should live up to clients' needs and desires all together for it to quick fulfillment. The commonness of worldwide advertising and the decline of global exchange interferences have brought about extraordinarily competitive markets for strong items. In today's free and aggressive markets, buyer inclinations and key characteristics of items have turned out to be so enhanced that companies that can meet these client desires will flourish and raise, while those that neglect to do as such will decrease. Allenby (1989) and Kannan and Wright (1991) suggest that the plan of fruitful advertising techniques requires a detailed indulgent of the structure of the item showcase and the examples of rivalry inside those business sectors. In this way, it is significant to gather

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advertise information to investigate market structures, particularly for strong cellular network that have entered their develop stage, characterized by developing network advances, absence of network separation and similarity in network qualities. The expanding rivalry, brand picture and state of mind toward network will incredibly effect on the buy choices of clients. Keeping in mind the end goal to position its items and brands, the producer needs to hold the consumer's disposition towards these variables. Thusly, it is key to have a superior comprehension of brand uncertainty.

Telecom industry is buildup of the significant number of enterprises and organizations giving phone service, information or incentive to customers and organizations, it is the fastest growing industry in Pakistan today with most amazing development rate in tele-communication around the world (Audi et al., 2021; Audi et al., 2022). Because of high development rate this industry has turned out to be backbone of Pakistanis economy. It is giving numerous work and speculation openings because of high revenues generated by means of huge number of clients of telecom segment. Along with circumstances, this industry additionally gives unlimited offices to convey and associate internationally in better, reliable and advanced way. Today IT segment of Pakistan can be considered as most developed mechanical segment of Pakistan. This industry is expected to develop by half in next 3 years and development rate may increment in future due to introduction of 3G innovation in cell phone administrations and new network access providing methods like DSL, broadband and Wi-Max all through the nation. As much as 1 million new clients are added to number of cell endorsers which remained at 91,442,341, by March 2009. There are many previous studies conduct for understanding the switching intention in telecommunication market. In past studies cellular market began to mark their services by different strategies to support a decent picture among shoppers (Park et al., 1986). Trivedi and Morgan (1996) found that the degree of brand switching can change over the time and the level of replacing services. One of the most important variables that impact customer switching is advertising. There are researchers that rejecting a few discoveries from past studies, Shukla (2004), satisfaction from services force customers to retain with the same service provider. In other case, service personnel were found to affect availability to switch, which implies that buyers might want to meet the new brand and see whether it coordinates their feelings (Malhotra & Malhotra, 2015; Ali & Audi, 2018). Further in this study result is based on customer switching in telecommunication sector is depend on person's feelings and other emotions.

According to our observation, there are some issues exist in telecommunication sector. In which, there are some important issues that takes time to addressed. From which recognize some major problems that exist in cellular industry. Therefore, network selling personnel are making inequalities between customers and high class customers. Give high class customer's more value and make difference between customers. Furthermore, in cellular industry customers face convenience problem, i.e. there are franchises not conveniently available in every area. Customer faces many troubles regarding this issue. Moreover, if customer relationship officer (CRO) is not much eligible to coordinate with customer and resolve their problem is the main issue through customer change their mind to switch their service provider. Likewise, one more important problem is to addressed that without inform to customer they make deduction from their account for different packages that are not usable.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Our research is based on a hypothetical model that is Justice Theory Model. This theory was initially distributed by Rawls (1971). Researcher is a thinker, who held the James Bryant Conant University Professorship at Harvard University, appropriated a couple books and many articles. The researcher is basically known, nevertheless, for his book "A Theory of Justice", it is a book which pushes to describe social value. The work has uncommonly influences current political thought. Equity hypothesis (justice theory) is a work of political theory and morals in which the researcher work on it. The book Justice as Fairness was an enhanced and shorter presentation of Rawls' hypothesis, distributed in 2001 with article encourage by Erin Kelly, one of his previous students. In this theory he tries to take care of the issue of distributive equity i.e. the socially transmission of the products in a general public by utilizing a differences of the gadget of the social contract. The importance of the theory is referred to as the Justice as Fairness in which Rawls (1975) concludes his two principles of justice one is the liberty of the principles and the second is the difference in the principle. This theory has two parts. The first part is about the social structures that outlines that the distribution must fulfill the necessities of fair or equal opportunities and the other part is about the principle that is difference in the principle means the social or economic inequalities. The term distributive justice means no other than the justice on the respect to distribution however, that would be the distribution of money, services or any other rare goods or rights. Who gets what, is the important question. In any case, the sincere way of distributive justice involves incredible discussion, and on a few levels Procedural justice is the possibility in which the justice the process resolves the discussion of the resources as well as the allocation of the resources. One of the parts of the procedural justice is

that it is connected with the examinations of the administrations of the equity and authentic/sincere system. The idea of the procedural justice is defined as the perceived fairness of the procedures, structures and the criteria utilized by the inventers to take after the base of the consequences of the discussion or collaboration (Blodgett et al. 1997, p. 189).

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According to the Greenberg (1993) the interactional justice identifying the communication issues matters a different build which he marked "informational justice". Informational justice notices to the roundness and trustworthiness of information which illuminates the purposes behind a negative event (Colquitt, 2001). A client's view of informational justice is damaged by the absence of clarifications gave to individual person regarding why the strategies were utilized as a part of a specific way or why the outcomes were passed on particularly (Greenberg, 1993; Colquitt, 2001; Colquitt et al., 2001). Instructive or informational has been for the most part was ignored in management advertising writing, and similarly starting late associated into the particular circumstance (Lee & Park, 2010). Observational research in administration has as of late given helps the four-part model of equity that interpersonal and educational equity exclusively affects administrative outcomes (Colquitt, 2001; Colquitt et al., 2001). For instance, Colquitt (2001) finds that interpersonal justice was associated with the helping conduct, though informational justice was associated with the collective regard.

Casado-Dí'az, Ma's-Ruiz and Kasper (2007), observes that the effects of anger and distributive justice which is explaining the satisfaction in double deviation situation. They have collected a sample by application of latent variable path analysis to the proposed model. The questions which is used in this study were taken from the relevant literatures and the interviews were conducted in this research by using a sample of individuals from the future population i.e. 26 members of the consumer organization. They have used the variables in this study is satisfaction with food recovery, anger with service recovery and distributive justice. Likewise, the data was tested by analysis of measurement model. The findings of the study are that the study is supporting the model and highlighting the importance of the specific recovery related emotions in double deviation contexts. The result shows that the emotion like anger plays a vital role in describing the satisfaction with service recovery. In the future customer satisfaction surveys might include the items that measure the specific emotions. This might increase the efficiency as executive tools.

Dayan and Benedetto (2008), observed the effect of justice (Procedural and interactional) on organizational performance and teamwork features. These researchers' surveyed 117 product managers and 314 firms for protect their research. Dayan and Colak (2008), find out that to exploring the function of procedural justice climate in product expansion the procedural justice climate gives the positive impact in the new invention and also the growing marketplace faster. Researchers use the theoretical approach to develop the tested and collected data from different Turkish company's manger which are 93 respondents. Most researchers using this Structural equation modeling to analyst its data. This method is more appropriate for these variables. Basically, the product manager was participated in this study form various industries and also telecommunication, food material etc. are included in it. The variable researcher uses it product innovation, product development, new product, marketing, furthermore, the systematic study in justice workplace and much more focused on the justice. Moreover, this justice using in the organization for a better outcome of the fairness and distributive justice. And quality treatment, moreover they explaining the effect of justice outcome in the organization and also for the satisfaction of job has been confirm by the researcher and also talking about the great interest in the justice individual and impact in the team work and team level , in the individual team many employees facing the difficulties in it because many time they changing their team again and again for that organization facing many trouble, they also talk about the in the previous studies point out that they talk about the

collectives and using the multiple dimension and also preference the group work for that group can willing give up for the grouping and also build the helpful relationship in group and interact with many people and come great outcome for the organization and better impact in the organization work conflict getting less day by day, the product innovation in the organization also effected the great impact in the firm because new thinking new creativity also impact in the workplace environment.

Matos et al. (2009), motive of this research was to discover the reason of loyalty and satisfaction differences between switching intension. This study was performing through survey, with data being assemble via Brazilian bank from 7,461 customers. The study data in this proposal is pinched from four challenging models was tested using ‘structural equation modeling technique’. In the first place, the study presents some key approaching into switching of product cost have Vital example of both feelings and manners loyalty. Industries must retain their employees within their self-due to maintain their moral and be competitive in market. Likewise, this study provides new upcoming that impact of satisfaction on loyalty is positive and very high important. Moreover, some other variables are also influence loyalty like commitment with consumer, switching product cost and faith. As well as, company’s reputation is based on their product or services via consumer satisfy their self and make good observation through experience. All the way through this paper, the impact of switching cost is directly affect the relationship between satisfaction loyalties. Dix and Phau (2010), discover the cause of channel switching intension among consumers. Information for this study was gathered from qualitative research in which they using pilot study to collect 100 sample sizes from the given population to understand the aspect that generates channel switching within TV consumers.

Gounaris, Dimitriadis and Stathakopoulos (2010), analyzed the customer’s behavioral intentions towards e-marketing or e-shopping which has an effect of service quality and satisfaction. They have collected the sample data from 240 people online. They generate randomly sample of 1052 online shoppers who are using database in Greece which is a leading internet provider. The variables they have considered are consumer behavior, electronic commerce and retailing. Additionally, the sample data was tested by using correlation/covariance matrix, correlation/covariance matrix and examination of competing models. The findings of the study suggest that information investigation included the examination of three opponent models utilizing basic conditions displaying. The won model uncovers that e-benefit quality positively affects e-fulfillment, while it additionally impacts, both straightforwardly and by implication through e-fulfillment, the buyer’s behavioral goals, to be specific site return to, verbal correspondence and repeat buying.

Biedenbach, Bengtsson and Marell (2015), evaluates that the examination of effects in the business-to-business settings according to the brand equity, satisfaction and switching cost. They have collected the sample data from Structural equation modeling in which they use 360 responses of CEOs and CFOs of an organization buying auditing consultancy services from one of the biggest four auditing companies. They variables have used in their research is switching costs, satisfaction, brand awareness, brand association, perceived quality and brand loyalty. Additionally, sample data were tested by applying descriptive statistics and correlations, measures and standardized loadings and structural model estimates and fit indices. Rai (2015), observes that the diminishing roles of employee’s mental health and the organizational justice in the identification of an organization. They have collected the sample data from a standard questionnaire in which a survey study was conducted in two multinational organizations which is located in northern and southern parts of the India. The sample size is 321, in which 80 percent were male, 20 percent were female and the average age of the sample is 29 years.

3. CONCEPTUAL MODEL

FIGURE 1:

3.1. MODEL HYPOTHESIS

- H1: Distributional Justice has a positive impact on switching intention of the users of mobile network.
- H2: Informational Justice has a positive impact on switching intention of the users of mobile network.
- H3: Interpersonal Justice has a negative impact on switching intention of the users of mobile network.
- H4: Procedural justice has a positive impact on switching intention of the users of mobile network.

4. METHODOLOGY

The approach which we are going to use in our study is quantitative approach because the data which we collect is simply based on numbers. It is a lot easier to collect and convert all the data into a form of chart. Quantitative research allows the researches to measure the data and analyze the data easily. In this research the relationship between the dependent and independent variable is studied in details it is the advantage of the type of research for the researchers because they are more ideal to study about the findings. This is the place a researcher has an issue and would like to see more about it. An exploratory research attempt is a push to undrain the strategy that will recover to future reviews or to realize whether what is being seen might be cleared up by the tilted of an eye existing theory. In this study we have used the explanatory research purpose to identify the causes and effects of the study that required. This purpose helped the study to recognize which variables are causes and which variables are effects of the causes and to inspect which type of relationship exist between the actual variables and the predicted effects. This research focuses on quantitative research design, which is based on empirical investigation by using statistical techniques. Basically, this research uses correlational research design as it best suits the research because there is a dependent variable that is brand switching over which impact and relationship of four independent variables; descriptive theory, procedural theory, informational theory and interpersonal theory, is analyzed. The data source which we use in our research is the primary data source. Essential information is customized to the necessities of the analyst. At the point when leading a review, specialists can position the questions that best gather the information that assistance with their review using studies, meets and direct observations. It can be either quantitative, centered around numbers and approximations, or subjective, as when manners or feelings are gathered and considered. In showcasing research, primary data gives the analyst a focused superiority. In any case, directing this examination is regularly excessive and boring. The target population of this study consists of the cellular user's female and male both investigating the particular group as (employees and university students). The targeted location of population is the users of Karachi, Pakistan. Our data is consisting of 475 survey papers which included 25 questions (5 question of each variable). The distribution of survey papers was face to face by filling questionnaires, the location is Iqra University Gulshan Campus and the most of the respondents are students. We collect 475 questionnaires from our valuable respondent from which 450 survey papers were usable and remaining 25 were outliers the reason of difference of 25 survey papers occurred because lack of interest of respondents. The data collection tool that we have used in the study is questionnaire, where we asked questions in a written and well organized manner by giving the answer choices from our target audience in order to collect information related to the topic. We select this tool because data can be collected relatively quickly as compare to other methods because the researcher's presence is not needed, when the questionnaire completed. This study uses non-probability sampling for conducting the research. Furthermore, convenience sampling is used as the data was gathered from the sample which was easily available, and there was easy access of the researchers to the sample. We use EFA to check the dimension/factors.

5. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

5.1. RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

Table 1

Variables	Items	Cronbach's alpha
DJ	5	.863
PJ	5	.835
INJ	5	.826
IJ	5	.847
SI	5	.834
Overall	25	.911

To observe the internal dependability of the item of questionnaire researchers perform reliability analysis. Cronbach's alpha (α) was used to explore the reliability of the instruments. Reliability is greater than 0.7 i.e. 70% is very good but in some cases it is on 0.6 or 0.5 i.e. 60% and 50% respectively (Sekaran et al., 2003). It is necessary to analyze the data from reliability analysis (Nunnally, 1978). Moreover, in this case reliability of the all five variables together is more than 70% that is acceptable. The value of Cronbach's alpha (α) (from 1 dependent and 4 independent variables)

that based on 25 items is 0.911 i.e. 91.1% this shows the consistency of the items. There is no such item exist from which we increase the reliability.

5.2. KAISER–MEYER–OLKIN AND BARTLETT’S TESTS OF SAMPLING ADEQUACY (KMO)

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.903
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	5316.204
	Df
	300
	Sig.
	.000

For the study of our sampling adequacy we used KMO and B Bartlett’s test of sphericity test values. For our situation the KMO esteem is 0.903 which fulfill the basic criteria which is recommended by Kaiser (1974). The bench mark which Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin set is 0.70 (70%). As indicated by the Kaiser (1974), the KMO esteem extending from 0.70 to 0.79 is considered as great example. Furthermore, the Bartlett'e trial of sphericity value of probability is 0.000 (which is under 0.05). it demonstrates the relationship between the things at the 5 percent level of importance is adequate and is satisfactory for further examination.

5.3. EXPLORATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS (EFA)

Table 3: Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component				
	Distributive Justice	Informational Justice	Switching Intention	Interpersonal Justice	Procedural Justice
DJ 1	.708				
DJ 2	.749				
DJ 3	.772				
DJ 4	.796				
DJ 5	.638				
IJ 1		.717			
IJ 2		.785			
IJ 3		.732			
IJ 4		.737			
IJ 5		.692			
SI 1			.747		
SI 2			.834		
SI 3			.815		
SI 4			.641		
SI 5			.783		
INJ 1				.739	
INJ 2				.763	
INJ 3				.677	
INJ 4				.750	
INJ 5				.636	
PJ 1					.744
PJ 2					.722
PJ 3					.660
PJ 4					.620
PJ 5					.591

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.

According to Emory and Cooper (1991) claims that the factor analysis can help the scholars in determining the resources of the factors. The first factor Distributive Justice which has five items with the loading are DJ1 is 0.708, DJ2 is 0.794, DJ3 is 0.772, DJ4 is 0.796 and DJ5 is 0.638. The second factor Informational Justice which has five items with the loadings are IJ1 is 0.717, IJ2 is 0.785, IJ3 is 0.732, IJ4 is 0.737 and IJ5 is 0.692. The third factor in our study is Switching Intention which also has five items with the loadings of each items are SI1 is 0.747, SI2 is 0.834, SI3 is 0.815, SI4 is 0.641 and SI5 is 0.783. The fourth factor is Interpersonal Justice with five items as well. Here the loading of each item is that INJ1 is 0.79, INJ2 0.763, INJ3 is 0.677, INJ4 is 0.750 and INJ5 is 0.636. The fifth factor is Procedural Justice it also has five items with the loading are PJ1 is 0.744, PJ2 is 0.722, PJ3 is 0.660, PJ4 is 0.620 and PJ5 is 0.591. Furthermore, the factor loadings for all items are extending from 0.55 to 0.84, which fulfill the base criteria of 0.30 for a specimen of 350 or above (Hair et.al., 1998).

Table 4: Standardized regression weights for the research model

Hypothesis	Variables	Regression Path	Estimated	P-values	Remarks
H1	Distributional Justice	ASI<--- ADJ	-.154	0.390	Accepted
H2	Informational justice	ASI<--- APJ	0.18	0.083	Accepted
H3	Interpersonal justice	ASI<--- AIJ	-.020	0.078	Accepted
H4	Procedural justice	ASI<--- AINJ	-.013	0.086	Accepted

6. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study lead us to the conclusion that distributional justice has a significant positive impact on switching intention of the users of mobile network. The switching intention of the users of mobile network is also positively impacted by informational justice. Whereas, Interpersonal justice has shown the tendency to negatively impact the intention of the users of mobile network. A positive impact of procedural justice has been depicted upon the intention of users of mobile network. So, in a nutshell, distributional, informational and procedural justice positively impact switching intention of the mobile network users, whereas, the case is vice versa for interpersonal justice.

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